

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF MONITORING AND EVALUATION IN THE EFFECTIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF DEPED PROGRAMS AND PROJECTS

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ABSTRACT

This study sought to assess the implementation of monitoring and evaluation (M&E) to track the effectiveness and sustainability of the Department of Education (DepEd) programs and projects. The researcher employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Survey questionnaires were distributed to all school heads and selected teachers from a sample of 25 public schools in Dumaguete City. The statistical tools used in this study included the mean, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and the t-test. The study revealed that the extent of M&E implementation was perceived as “very high” by both school heads and teachers across all dimensions considered. Moreover, the effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects were assessed by both school heads and teachers to a “very high” extent. Additionally, the results indicated a statistically significant relationship between the implementation of M&E and its perceived effectiveness within the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD). Furthermore, there was a statistically significant difference between the assessments of the two respondent groups regarding the extent of M&E implementation throughout the division. Lastly, the results of the study revealed a significant difference in how school heads and teachers perceive the effectiveness of M&E activities. While both groups share similar perspectives on the effectiveness of these activities under the SGOD, they express these views with varying degrees of magnitude.

Keywords: *DepEd programs, effectiveness, M&E, monitoring, evaluation, school heads, teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Effective project implementation is essential in the education sector, as it directly influences the quality of learning outcomes, equity of access, and the effective use of public resources. In this context, monitoring and evaluation (M&E) are indispensable in confirming that education initiatives are implemented as intended and that resources are utilized responsibly. However, weak M&E systems have been shown to exacerbate existing inequalities and undermine program effectiveness. A major global issue is the limited technical capacity of institutions to design, implement, and maintain effective M&E systems. Numerous developing countries lack trained personnel, standardized tools, and functional systems for data analysis and utilization. This results in weak evidence-based decision-making and poor program outcomes. Capacity constraints continue to limit the effectiveness of M&E systems in many countries (World Bank, 2021). In a study examining emergency distance schooling in Kazakhstan, Durrani and Makhmetova (2024) found that inadequate monitoring and evaluation mechanisms contributed to widening educational disparities, particularly among students from disadvantaged backgrounds. Their findings emphasize how critical M&E is in safeguarding equity and certifying that education interventions achieve their intended impact, especially during periods of disruption or reform.

To address the pressing issues of the quality of programs and projects implementation, the global framework of Sustainable Development Goal 4 provides a structured set of targets and indicators that strengthen M&E in education programs and projects. SDG 4's emphasis on equity, access, and quality learning outcomes supports education systems in developing robust data collection and reporting processes that ensure gaps in M&E, such as inconsistent data and a lack of standardized benchmarks, are addressed through internationally recognized indicators (UNESCO, 2024). In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has developed a structured, far-reaching approach to address these concerns by implementing the Basic Education M&E Framework (BEMEF). The BEMEF guides operating units at all governance levels to gather evidence, track performance, and use findings to improve program implementation and outcomes (DepEd, 2022).

In the Schools Division of Dumaguete City, several programs and projects are implemented to support both local and national education goals. However, questions remain regarding how consistently M&E processes are applied, the challenges encountered by implementers, and the extent to which M&E results contribute to program improvement and long-term impact. While literature affirms the importance of data use and feedback mechanisms for performance improvement, few studies analyse how variations in implementation quality, capacity constraints, and utilization of M&E results affect substantive outcomes at the division level of education systems. This shortfall stresses the need for the current study. Investigating how M&E practices contribute to the successful execution of programs and projects within the division can reinforce data-driven decision-making and improve the impact of basic education initiatives. While the importance of M&E is widely acknowledged, there appear to be inconsistencies in how these processes are applied and perceived. The level of implementation, the overall effectiveness of M&E, and the challenges encountered vary significantly across individuals and roles, thereby highlighting the need for a deeper investigation into how

M&E practices influence the overall impact of educational initiatives. According to VP Sarah Duterte in her speech during the 1st M&E Conference in General Santos City, last June 20, 2023, M&E is far from being a mere technical requirement, but functions as a vital force within the organization. It cultivates transparency, reinforces accountability, and nurtures an ongoing cycle of learning and growth. Grounding education reforms in solid evidence and data supports the continuous refinement of initiatives and steers decision-making toward choices that more effectively advance learners' outcomes.

Research Questions

1. As perceived by school heads and teachers, to what extent is M&E implemented to track school programs and projects in terms of:
 - 1.1 relevance and alignment;
 - 1.2 effectiveness of outcomes;
 - 1.3 efficiency of implementation;
 - 1.4 sustainability and institutionalization;
 - 1.5 equity and inclusiveness;
 - 1.6 stakeholders' participation;
 - 1.7 impact; and
 - 1.8 monitoring and data quality?
2. To what extent is the effectiveness and sustainability of the DepEd programs and projects as perceived by school heads and teachers?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and its extent of effectiveness?
4. Is there a significant difference in assessment between that of school heads and that of teachers as to the extent of implementation of M&E?
5. Is there a significant difference in the school heads' and teachers' perceptions as to the extent of effectiveness of M&E?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a quantitative, descriptive correlational research design to determine the relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and the effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects. The descriptive component was used to assess the level of M&E implementation across its dimensions, while the correlational component examined the relationship between M&E implementation and program effectiveness and sustainability. This design is appropriate as it allows the measurement of variables as they naturally occur without manipulation.

Research environment. The study was conducted in all 18 public elementary and 7 secondary schools in the division of Dumaguete City. The Schools Division of Dumaguete City, established in 1975, is situated in Barangay

Taclobo, Dumaguete City. This is a small division with accessible schools, where M&E practices are actively implemented to gather objective information. This information can

enhance decision-making and improve the delivery of school services for basic education, which ultimately contributes to better educational outcomes. The division is also guided and mandated by the DepEd Mission, Vision, and Core Values to provide for the establishment and maintenance of a complete, adequate, and integrated system of basic education relevant to the goal of national development. To achieve the committed strategic directions, SDO Dumaguete has conceptualized a program support framework called Achieving greater HEIGHTS, the Chada Way, which gives emphasis on the various programs and projects initiated and implemented by the division.

Research respondents. The respondents of the study were the school heads taken universally, while the teacher respondents were subjected to sampling, using Yamane's formula to get the accurate sample size and distributed proportionately among the different schools of the division of Dumaguete City. The required samples in each school were randomly picked using systematic sampling with a random start.

Research instrument. The main tool used in this study is a survey questionnaire. It is a researcher-made tool that underwent reliability testing and validation by a panel of experts who are specialists in this line. Prior to the formulation of the questionnaire, the researcher made a review of related studies, books, and articles, and consulted with her adviser to ensure that the intention of the study would be covered. For its reliability, the questionnaire was administered first as a dry run to a group of teachers who are not part of the sample. The test and re-test method were used to ensure coefficient stability. The questionnaire is organized into three sections.

Part I presents the disclosure statement to ensure that the respondents are informed about the purpose and ethical considerations of the study. Part II gathers the respondents' demographic and professional profiles. Part III evaluates the level of implementation and the effectiveness of M&E across several dimensions: relevance and alignment, outcome effectiveness, implementation efficiency, sustainability and institutionalization, equity and inclusiveness, stakeholder participation, and the quality of monitoring and data. All responses are captured using a five-point Likert scale, with options ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree."

Research procedure. In the conduct of this study, the researcher first sent a letter requesting to conduct the study and a letter of recommendation from the dean of the graduate school, with the attached copy of the questionnaire, to the Schools Division Superintendent of DepEd Dumaguete City. Upon approval, the questionnaires were distributed to the school heads and teachers who were included in the study. The retrieval was done right after the respondents completed the questionnaire. Results were tallied, analysed, and interpreted.

Statistical Treatment of the Data. The tools the researcher used in analysing data were the following:

Mean (\bar{x}). This was used to determine teachers' and school heads' perceptions of the implementation of M&E to track the effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson r). This tool is used to determine the relationship between variables. In this study, it was used to establish the relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and the effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects, vice versa. **t-test.** This was used to test significant differences in the perceptions of school heads and teachers regarding the implementation of M&E to track the effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects.

Scope of the Study. This study focuses on determining the relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and the effectiveness and sustainability of the DepEd programs and projects. Specifically, the scope of the study covers M&E implementation in terms of relevance and alignment, effectiveness of outcomes, efficiency of implementation, sustainability and institutionalization, equity and inclusiveness, stakeholders' participation, and monitoring and data quality. The respondents of the study were limited to school heads and selected teachers involved in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of DepEd programs and projects during the specified school year. The study was conducted within Dumaguete City public elementary and secondary schools under DepEd and utilized a quantitative research design employing a structured survey questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument.

Limitations of the study. In the conduct of this study, the researcher recognized some limitations. The study relied on self-reported data, which may be subject to response bias and variations in the respondents' perceptions and experiences. The findings are also limited to the selected respondents and geographic coverage and may not be fully generalizable to all DepEd programs. Moreover, the study does not include direct measurement of long-term learner outcomes or financial impact assessments. External factors such as policy changes, funding constraints, and unforeseen disruptions during program implementation were beyond the control of the study and may influence the results. Lastly, the findings could be construed as true only for the schools covered in the division and not necessarily for other divisions.

To address these limitations, control mechanisms were employed, including the use of validated research instruments, standardized data collection procedures, clear operational definitions of variables, and appropriate statistical controls to minimize measurement errors and enhance the reliability and validity of the findings.

RESULTS

The data presented in Table 1.1 show that both school heads and teachers perceive the implementation of M&E activities as highly relevant and well-aligned with the strategic directions of the Department of Education.

Table 1.1

Extent of Implementation of M&E as perceived by School Heads and Teachers in terms of Its Relevance and Alignment

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
The program/project				
1. Aligns M & E activities with DepEd strategic goals and K-12 Curriculum.	4.84	S A	4.5	S A
2. Satisfies stakeholders as to its perceived usefulness.	4.71	S A	4.3	S A
3. Addresses specific educational concerns and issues.	4.73	S A	4.5	S A
4. Considers local needs and context in program design.	4.67	S A	4.3	S A
5. Involves teachers, students, parents, and LGU in planning and development.	4.67	S A	4.4	S A
Composite Mean	4.72	S A	4.4	S A
Extent of Implementation	Very High		Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.2 presents the extent of implementation of M&E as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of the effectiveness of outcomes.

Table 1.2
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of Its Effectiveness of Outcomes

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teacher s n = 277	
		V D		
1. Increases the percentage of beneficiaries who achieved learning outcomes.	4.65	S A	4.4	S A
2. Achieves its intended objectives.	4.67	S A	4.2	S A
3. Completes 100% of planned deliverables.	4.54	S A	4.3	S A
4. Reduces dropout or repetition rates in target areas.	4.56	S A	4.2	S A
5. Improves teachers' practices and instructional competence.	4.64	S A	4.3	S A

Composite Mean	4.61	S A	4.3 2	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.3 presents the extent of implementation of M&E as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of its efficiency of implementation.

Table 1.3
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of Its Efficiency of Implementation

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	Verbal Description	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Utilizes resources such as time and manpower well.	4.61	S A	4.40	S A
2. Completes activities on schedule.	4.48	S A	4.25	S A
3. Adheres to planned program design.	4.63	S A	4.36	S A
4. Makes human material and technological resources available during implementation.	4.61	S A	4.24	S A
5. Utilizes the budget as planned.	4.59	S A	4.34	S A
Composite Mean	4.58	S A	4.32	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.4 presents the extent of implementation of M&E in terms of sustainability and institutionalization, as assessed by school heads and teachers. the school system.

Table 1.4
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of Its Sustainability & Institutionalization

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. Provides policy and budget line to make the program part of the regular system.	4.63	S A	4.27	S A
2. Involves the community and LGU for program continuity.	4.59	S A	4.50	S A
3. Integrates program practices into school operations.	4.73	S A	4.44	S A
4. Provides a mechanism to ensure continuity of skills and leadership.	4.67	S A	4.35	S A
5. Provides opportunity for the program to be expanded or replicated in other divisions/regions.	4.58	S A	4.28	S A
Composite Mean	4.64	S A	4.37	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.5 presents the extent of implementation of M&E in terms of equity and inclusiveness as perceived by school heads and teachers.

Table 1.5
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of Its Equity and Inclusiveness

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
		V D		V D

1. Increases participation rate of indigenous people, learners with disabilities, and other marginalized groups.	4.46	S A	4.42	S A
2. Observes gender parity index in enrolment and achievement.	4.59	S A	4.28	S A
3. Provides inclusive learning materials and facilities.	4.60	S A	4.35	S A
4. Gives access to students with limited connectivity or devices.	4.54	S A	4.30	S A
5. Serves marginalized and underserved learners.	4.56	S A	4.32	S A
Composite Mean	4.55	S A	4.33	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.6 presents the extent of implementation of M&E relative to stakeholders' participation, as assessed by school heads and teachers.

Table 1.6
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of Its Stakeholders' Participation

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
1. Consults diverse stakeholders in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of the program.	4.65	S A	4.34	S A
2. Establishes feedback mechanisms such as grievance redress system and suggestion box.	4.66	S A	4.35	S A
3. Involves LGU, parents and community in projects/activities under the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD).	4.69	S A	4.55	S A

4. Keeps stakeholders informed of the progress of programs and projects.	4.73	S A	4.36	S A
5. Acknowledges stakeholders' participation during meetings and programs.	4.75	S A	4.50	S A
Composite Mean	4.70	S A	4.42	S A
Extent of Implementation	Very High		Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.7 shows the extent of M&E implementation as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of the impact of the programs and projects.

Table 1.7
Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms of the Impact of the Projects and Programs

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
1. Manifests changes in community literacy or educational attainment levels.	4.71	S A	4.27	S A
2. Manifests employment or further education rates of graduates.	4.60	S A	4.28	S A
3. Gives access to marginalized group.	4.52	S A	4.30	S A
4. Raises community socio-economic level.	4.62	S A	4.25	S A
5. Improves academic performance of learners.	4.59	S A	4.46	S A
Composite Mean	4.61	S A	4.31	S A
Extent of Implementation	Very High		Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.8 presents the extent of implementation of M&E, focusing on monitoring processes and data quality.

Table 1.8**Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers in Terms Its Monitoring and Data Quality**

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
1. Submits M&E Report regularly and on time.	4.59	S A	4.42	S A
2. Utilizes authentic and updated data in the decision-making process.	4.67	S A	4.38	S A
3. Reports accurate and consistent data versus actual results.	4.67	S A	4.32	S A
4. Checks data as to its accuracy.	4.69	S A	4.33	S A
5. Stores data safely for future referrals.	4.65	S A	4.34	S A
Composite Mean	4.65	S A	4.36	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 1.9 presents the summary of the extent of implementation of M&E as perceived by school heads (N = 52) and teachers (n = 277) across eight key indicators.

Table 1.9**Summary Table as to the Extent of Implementation of M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers**

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		VI		
Relevance and Alignment	4.72	VHE	4.4	VH 2 E
Effectiveness of Outcomes	4.61	VHE	4.3	VH 2 E
Efficiency of Implementation	4.58	VHE	4.3	VH 2 E
Sustainability & Institutionalization	4.64	VHE	4.3	VH 7 E
Equity & Inclusiveness	4.55	VHE	4.3	VH 3 E
Stakeholders' Participation	4.70	VHE	4.4	VH 2 E

Impact of the Project & Program	4.61	VHE	4.3	VH
			1	E
Monitoring and Data Quality	4.65	VHE	4.3	VH
			6	E
Average	4.63	VHE	4.3	VH
			6	E

Note: Verbal Interpretation (VI): 4.21–5.00 Very High Extent (VHE); 3.41–4.20 High Extent (HE); 2.61–3.40 Moderate Extent (ME); 1.81–2.60 Low Extent (LE); 1.00–1.80 Very Low Extent (VLE).

Table 2.1 presents the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD) in terms of Relevance and Alignment.

Table 2.1
Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Relevance and Alignment

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	Verbal Description (VD)	Mean	Verbal Description (VD)
1. Aligns M & E activities with DepEd strategic goals and K-12 Curriculum.	4.60	Strongly Agree (SA)	4.40	Strongly Agree (SA)
2. Satisfies stakeholders as to its perceived usefulness.	4.52	Agree (A)	4.27	Agree (A)
3. Addresses specific educational concerns and issues.	4.44	Agree (A)	4.26	Agree (A)
4. Considers local needs and context in program design.	4.48	Agree (A)	4.35	Agree (A)
5. Involves teachers, students, parents, and LGU in planning and development.	4.43	Agree (A)	4.38	Agree (A)
Composite Mean	4.49	Agree (A)	4.33	Agree (A)
Extent of Effectiveness		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.2 presents the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD) in terms of Effectiveness of Outcomes.

Table 2.2

Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Effectiveness of Outcomes

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
1. Increases the percentage of beneficiaries who achieved learning outcomes.	4.48	S A	4.21	S A
2. Achieves its intended objectives.	4.50	S A	4.26	S A
3. Completes 100% of planned deliverables.	4.44	S A	4.22	S A
4. Reduces dropout or repetition rates in target areas.	4.33	S A	4.28	S A
5. Improves teachers' practices and instructional competence.	4.58	S A	4.25	S A
Composite Mean	4.46	S A	4.24	S A
Extent of Effectiveness		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.3 presents the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD in terms of Efficiency of Implementation.

Table 2.3

Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Efficiency of Implementation

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
		V D		
1. Utilizes resources such as time and manpower well.	4.38	S A	4.28	S A
2. Completes activities on schedule.	4.39	S A	4.20	A
3. Adheres to planned program design.	4.48	S A	4.30	S A
4. Makes human material and technological resources available during implementation.	4.47	S A	4.18	A

5. Utilizes the budget as planned.	4.45	S A	4.36	S A
Composite Mean	4.43	S A	4.26	S A
Extent of Effectiveness		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.4 presents the extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of Sustainability and Institutionalization.

Table 2.4
Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Sustainability and Institutionalization

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	VD	VD	VD	VD
1. Provides policy and budget line to make the program part of the regular system.	4.40	S A	4.46	S A
2. Involves the community and LGU for program continuity.	4.50	S A	4.38	S A
3. Integrates program practices into school operations.	4.54	S A	4.20	A
4. Provides a mechanism to ensure continuity of skills and leadership.	4.46	S A	4.19	A
5. Provides opportunity for the program to be expanded or replicated in other divisions/regions.	4.45	S A	4.38	S A
Composite Mean	4.47	S A	4.32	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.5 presents the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD in terms of Equity and Inclusiveness.

Table 2.5
Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Equity and Inclusiveness

Indicators	School Heads		Teacher s	
	N = 52		n = 277	
		V D		V D
1. Increases participation rate of indigenous people, learners with disabilities, and other marginalized groups.	4.38	S A	4.3 3	S A
2. Observes gender parity index in enrolment and achievement.	4.42	S A	4.3 1	S A
3. Provides inclusive learning materials and facilities.	4.44	S A	4.1 8	A
4. Gives access to students with limited connectivity or devices.	4.38	S A	4.1 9	A
5. Serves marginalized and underserved learners.	4.50	S A	4.2 6	S A
Composite Mean	4.42	S A	4.2 5	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.6 presents the extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD in terms of Stakeholders' Participation, as assessed by school heads and teachers.

Table 2.6
Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Stakeholders' Participation

Indicators	School Heads		Teachers	
	N = 52		n = 277	
		V D		V D
1. Consults diverse stakeholders in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of the program.	4.48	S A	4.2 9	S A

2. Establishes feedback mechanism such as grievance redress system and suggestion box.	4.41	S A	4.2 7	S A
3. Involves LGU, parents and community in projects/activities under the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD).	4.54	S A	4.3 0	S A
4. Keeps stakeholders informed of the progress of programs and projects.	4.56	S A	4.2 8	S A
5. Acknowledges stakeholders' participation during meetings and programs.	4.58	S A	4.3 1	S A
Composite Mean	4.51	S A	4.2 9	S A
Extent of Implementation		Very High	Very High	

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.7 presents the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD in terms of the Impact of the Projects and Programs.

Table 2.7
Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to the Impact of the Projects and Programs

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	VD	VD	VD	VD
1. Manifests changes in community literacy or educational attainment levels.	4.55	S A	4.19	A
2. Manifests employment or further education rates of graduates.	4.43	S A	4.17	A
3. Gives access to marginalized group.	4.44	S A	4.23	S A
4. Raises community socio-economic level.	4.40	S A	4.20	A
5. Improves academic performance of learners.	4.48	S A	4.26	S A
Composite Mean	4.46	S A	4.21	S A

Extent of Implementation

Very High

Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.8 details the perceived extent of effectiveness of DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD in terms of Monitoring and Data Quality.

Table 2.8

Extent of Effectiveness of the DepEd Program and Projects Under the SGOD as Perceived by the School Heads and Teachers as to Monitoring and Data Quality

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
1. Submits M&E Report regularly and on time.	4.45	S A	4.3 7	SA
2. Utilizes authentic and updated data in the decision-making process.	4.49	S A	4.2 8	SA
3. Reports accurate and consistent data versus actual results.	4.51	S A	4.2 6	SA
4. Checks data as to its accuracy.	4.53	S A	4.2 9	SA
5. Stores data safely for future referrals.	4.52	S A	4.3 6	SA
Composite Mean	4.50	S A	4.3 1	SA
Extent of Implementation		Very High		Very High

Note: Verbal Description (VD): 4.21–5.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/Very High Extent; 3.41–4.20 Agree (A)/High Extent; 2.61–3.40 Neutral (N)/Moderate Extent; 1.81–2.60 Disagree (D)/Low Extent; 1.00–1.80 Strongly Disagree (SD)/Very Low Extent.

Table 2.9 presents a summary of the perceived extent of effectiveness of M&E for DepEd programs and projects under the SGOD.

Table 2.9

Summary Table as to the Extent of Effectiveness of the M&E as Perceived by School Heads and Teachers

Indicators	School Heads N = 52		Teachers n = 277	
	Mean	VD	Mean	VD
Relevance and Alignment	4.49	VHE	4.3 3	VH E
Effectiveness of Outcomes	4.46	VHE	4.2 4	VH E

Efficiency of Implementation	4.43	VHE	4.2	VH
			6	E
Sustainability & Institutionalization	4.47	VHE	4.3	VH
			2	E
Equity & Inclusiveness	4.42	VHE	4.4	VH
			1	E
Stakeholders' Participation	4.51	VHE	4.2	VH
			9	E
Impact of the Project & Program	4.46	VHE	4.2	VH
			1	E
Monitoring and Data Quality	4.50	VHE	4.3	VH
			1	E
Average:	4.47	VHE	4.3	VH
			0	E

Note: Verbal Interpretation (VI): 4.21–5.00 Very High Extent (VHE); 3.41–4.20 High Extent (HE); 2.61–3.40 Moderate Extent (ME); 1.81–2.60 Low Extent (LE); 1.00–1.80 Very Low Extent (VLE).

Table 3 presents the test on the relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and its extent of effectiveness.

Table 3
Test on Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of M&E and Its Extent of Effectiveness

Variables	r	Decision Rule	Remarks
Extent of Implementation and Effectiveness of M&E in terms of:			
Relevance & Alignment	0.651	Reject Ho	Significant
	5		
Effectiveness of Outcomes	0.689	Reject Ho	Significant
	7		
Efficiency of Implementation	0.660	Reject Ho	Significant
	6		
Sustainability & Institutionalization	0.675	Reject Ho	Significant
	8		
Equity & Inclusiveness	0.760	Reject Ho	Significant
	8		
Stakeholders' Participation	0.611	Reject Ho	Significant
	5		
Impact of the Project/Program	0.625	Reject Ho	Significant
	9		
Monitoring & Data Quality	0.747	Reject Ho	Significant
	5		
Overall:	0.722	Reject Ho	Significant
	5		

r significant level at 0.05, 50 df = 0.2732

Interpretation of r;

± 0.01 to ± 0.19	Negligible relationship
± 0.20 to ± 0.29	Weak relationship
± 0.30 to ± 0.39	Moderate relationship
± 0.40 to ± 0.69	Strong relationship
± 0.70 to Higher	Very strong relationship

Table 4 presents the test on the significant difference in the perceptions of school heads and teachers as to the extent of implementation of M&E.

Table 4
Test on Significant Difference in the Perception of School Heads and Teachers as to the Extent of Implementation of M&E

Variables	\bar{x}	statistics	df	p-value	Difference	Decision Rule	Remarks
Relevance & Alignment							
School Heads	4.72	3.66	51	0.001	0.299	Reject H_0	Significant
Teachers	4.42						
Effectiveness of Outcomes							
School Heads	4.61	3.49	51	0.001	0.292	Reject H_0	Significant
Teachers	4.32						
Efficiency of Implementation							
School Heads	4.58	2.65	51	0.011	0.257	Reject H_0	Significant
Teachers	4.32						
Sustainability & Institutionalization							
School Heads	4.64	4.38	51	0.006	0.252	Reject H_0	Significant
Teachers	4.37						
Equity & Inclusiveness							
School Heads	4.55	2.22	51	0.031	0.220	Reject H_0	Significant
Teachers	4.33						
Stakeholder's Participation							
School Heads	4.70	3.48	51		0.271		

Teachers	4.42			0.001		Reject H _o	Significant
Impact of the Project & Programs							
School Heads	4.61	3.25	51	0.002	0.302	Reject H _o	Significant
Teachers	4.31						
Monitoring & Data Quality							
School Heads	4.65	2.51	51	0.005	0.288	Reject H _o	Significant
Teachers	4.36						
Overall		3.25	51	0.002	0.268	Reject H _o	Significant

Significant level = 0.05

Table 5 presents the test on the significant difference in the perceptions of school heads and teachers as to the extent of effectiveness of M&E.

Table 5
Test on Significant Difference in the Perception of School Heads and Teachers as to the Extent of Effectiveness of M&E

Variables	\bar{x}	df	p-value	Difference	Decision Rule	Remarks
Relevance & Alignment						
School Heads	4.49	51	0.089	0.160	Do not Reject H _o	Not Significant
Teachers	4.33					
Effectiveness of Outcomes						
School Heads	4.46	51	0.005	0.220	Reject H _o	Significant
Teachers	4.24					
Efficiency of Implementation						
School Heads	4.43	51	0.067	0.170	Do not Reject H _o	Not Significant
Teachers	4.26					
Sustainability & Institutionalization						
School Heads	4.47	51	0.127	0.148	Do not Reject H _o	Not Significant
Teachers	4.32					
Equity & Inclusiveness						

School Heads	4.41	51	0.07	0.170	Do not Reject H _o	Not Significant
Teachers	4.25		3			
Stakeholder's Participation						
School Heads	4.51	51	0.01	0.224	Reject H _o	Significant
Teachers	4.29		2			
Impact of the Project & Programs						
School Heads	4.46	51	0.01	0.247	Reject H _o	Significant
Teachers	4.21		5			
Monitoring & Data Quality						
School Heads	4.50	51	0.06	0.191	Do not Reject H _o	Not Significant
Teachers	4.31		6			
Overall		51	0.01	0.204	Reject H _o	Significant
			9			

Significant level = 0.05

DISCUSSION

From the data gathered, the following salient findings are hereby presented:

1. Extent of Monitoring and Evaluation to track school programs and projects

1.1 Relevance and Alignment

The data presented in Table 1.1 show that both school heads and teachers perceive the implementation of M&E activities as highly relevant and well-aligned with the strategic directions of the Department of Education. The composite mean for school heads (4.72) and teachers (4.42), both interpreted as “Very High,” indicate a shared belief that M&E systems in the division are strongly integrated with curricular goals, stakeholder needs, contextual realities, and addresses specific educational concerns and issues. Among the indicators, school heads gave the highest rating ($\bar{X} = 4.84$) to the alignment of M&E with DepEd’s strategic goals and the K–12 Curriculum, while teachers likewise reported strong agreement ($\bar{X} = 4.52$). This high alignment supports current literature emphasizing that coherence between institutional monitoring mechanisms and national education policies strengthens program implementation, decision-making, and accountability (Akram et al., 2021). When M&E systems are directly tied to curricular standards and organizational priorities, schools are better positioned to evaluate the extent to which learning outcomes and performance targets are being achieved.

Nonetheless, the consistently higher ratings from school heads compared to teachers reflect a common pattern observed in implementation studies, where administrators tend to view policy execution more favorably than frontline actors, who often confront operational constraints more directly (Komba, 2022). This perceptual difference may indicate variations in communication, workload, or access to M&E training, stressing the need to explore teacher perspectives more deeply in future qualitative investigations.

Overall, the results demonstrate that the M&E system is widely perceived as highly relevant, well-aligned, and supportive of DepEd's strategic educational goals. Stakeholders recognize its value in addressing local needs, informing instructional planning, and strengthening collaborative governance. These findings affirm the integral role of M&E in enhancing the responsiveness and effectiveness of education programs and in guiding continuous improvement efforts across schools.

1.2 Effectiveness of Outcomes

Table 1.2 presents the extent of implementation of M&E as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of the effectiveness of outcomes. The data revealed that both school heads and teachers perceive the M&E system as highly effective in facilitating quality intended outcomes of educational interventions. The composite mean of school heads (4.61) and teachers (4.32) both fall under the "Very High Extent," suggesting strong consensus on the overall utility of M&E in enhancing school performance and learning delivery. The pattern of slightly higher ratings among school heads suggests potential perceptual gaps, particularly teachers' on-the-ground challenges in translating M&E data into classroom practice. Despite this difference, the consistently high ratings from both groups emphasize the belief that M&E processes are functioning effectively within the schools (Nederhof, 2020).

Nevertheless, strong agreement across all indicators affirms that M&E is perceived as a valuable mechanism that enhances program accountability, strengthens implementation, informs instruction, and contributes to improved learning outcomes. Overall, the results indicate a healthy M&E culture characterized by positive perceptions of its effectiveness.

1.3 Efficiency of Implementation

Table 1.3 presents the extent of implementation of M&E as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of its efficiency of implementation. The results demonstrated a very high extent of implementation of M&E efficiency as perceived by both school heads and teachers, with composite means of 4.58 and 4.32, respectively, indicating strong agreement across all indicators. These findings suggest that core operational components of M&E resource utilization, schedule adherence, fidelity to program design, availability of human and technological resources, and budget utilization are functioning efficiently within the school system. The consistently high ratings affirm that respondents perceive time, manpower, and resources as well-managed, paralleling contemporary literature which emphasizes that structured resource utilization is essential in achieving effective M&E implementation and reducing operational delays (Akram et al., 2021).

Notably, school heads consistently rated efficiency slightly higher than teachers, a pattern documented in previous research where administrators often perceive systems as more effectively implemented due to their involvement in planning, resource allocation, and oversight, whereas teachers encounter day-to-day operational challenges that may moderate their assessments (Komba, 2022). These findings suggest that core operational components of M&E resource utilization, schedule adherence, fidelity to program design, availability of human and technological resources, and budget utilization are functioning efficiently within the school system.

The consistently high ratings affirm that the respondents perceive time, manpower, and resources as well-managed, paralleling contemporary literature. This result emphasizes that structured resource utilization is essential in achieving effective M&E implementation and reducing operational delays (Akram et al., 2021).

1.4 Sustainability and Institutionalization

Table 1.4 presents the extent of implementation of M&E in terms of sustainability and institutionalization, as assessed by school heads and teachers. The composite means of 4.64 for school heads and 4.37 for teachers both fall within the verbal description “Strongly Agree,” interpreted as a very high extent of implementation. This suggests that both groups perceive M&E components related to sustainability and institutionalization as being well-integrated and effectively practiced within the school system. “Provision of policy and budget line to ensure that programs become part of the regular system” received high ratings from both groups, reflecting a strong perception that M&E is supported by institutional policies and financial structures.

According to Görgens and Kusek (2020), the long-term sustainability of M&E systems depends on stable budget allocation and policy integration, which enhance implementation continuity. Stakeholder collaboration remains a crucial component in sustaining educational programs, as seen in the results. As noted by Bamberger et al. (2021), strong local partnerships contribute to institutional ownership and sustainability of evaluation systems.

Meanwhile, “integrating program practices into school operations” also obtained very high ratings, which suggests that M&E practices have been effectively mainstreamed. Consistent with this, Preskill and Torres (2020) emphasized that institutionalization occurs when evaluation practices become part of routine organizational processes, shaping decision-making and instructional strategies.

In terms of “ensuring continuity of skills and leadership,” school heads strongly agreed, while teachers rated it slightly lower, though still within the high range. This implies that capacity-building mechanisms are evident but may be experienced differently across roles. Daly et al. (2023) noted that leadership continuity and evaluator competencies affect how consistently M&E systems function across school levels.

Finally, “providing opportunities for program expansion or replication” received ratings showing that both groups believe that the current M&E implementation enables

scalability. According to UNESCO, replicability is a hallmark of strong institutionalization, enabling programs to be adapted across regions once sound M&E systems are in place. In sum, the results affirm that sustainability and institutionalization mechanisms of M&E are perceived as robust and well-embedded in the school system, indicating strong program continuity, stakeholder engagement, and policy support.

1.5 Equity and Inclusiveness

Table 1.5 presents the extent of implementation of M&E in terms of equity and inclusiveness as perceived by school heads and teachers. Both groups registered verbal descriptions of Strongly Agree, corresponding to a Very High Extent of Implementation. The composite means of 4.55 for school heads and 4.33 for teachers indicate consistently positive perceptions of how M&E processes promote inclusive and equitable education within schools. The first indicator, “increases participation rate of indigenous people, learners with disabilities, and other marginalized groups,” obtained weighted means of 4.46 for school heads and 4.42 for teachers, both interpreted as very high. This finding affirms the strong alignment of school practices with national and global frameworks advocating inclusive access to education.

According to UNESCO (2020), inclusive systems ensure that disadvantaged learners fully participate in academic programs when institutional practices consciously address barriers to access. Similarly, DepEd’s policies on Indigenous Peoples Education and inclusive programs emphasize equitable participation across diverse learner groups (DepEd, 2021).

The second indicator, “Observes gender parity index in enrolment and achievement,” falls under a very high extent of implementation for both respondents. This indicates that schools are consistently monitoring gender related disparities and ensuring balanced participation among male, female, and gender diverse learners. The results reinforce international standards showing that gender responsive monitoring systems strengthen overall school equity (UNGEI & UNICEF, 2022). Regarding the provision of “inclusive learning materials and facilities,” the means affirm that learning resources are accessible and responsive to diverse learner needs. This is consistent with DepEd’s commitment to Universal Design for Learning (UDL), which underscores the need for adaptive, flexible, and accessible learning materials (DepEd, 2020).

Meanwhile, the fourth indicator, “Gives access to students with limited connectivity or devices,” reflects sustained efforts of schools to address digital equity, particularly during and after the shift to blended and technology-supported learning. UNESCO (2021) asserted that ensuring digital access remains a critical dimension of educational inclusiveness in the post-pandemic context. Lastly, the indicator “serves marginalized and underserved learners” reinforces the perception that M&E initiatives strongly guide schools in identifying, prioritizing, and responding to the needs of the most vulnerable. The World Bank (2023) highlights that data-driven M&E is essential in ensuring that interventions truly address inequities among underserved populations. The consistently high ratings across all indicators suggest strong institutional commitment to inclusive and

equitable education, supported by effective M&E and equity-driven initiatives in the educational system.

1.6 Stakeholders' Participation

Table 1.6 presents the extent of implementation of M&E relative to stakeholders' participation, as assessed by school heads and teachers. The composite means of 4.70 for school heads and 4.42 for teachers indicate a Very High Extent of implementation based on the verbal description scale. These findings demonstrate that stakeholders' participation is perceived as a well-established and consistently practiced component of M&E within the school system.

Indicator 1, which assesses the extent to which diverse stakeholders are consulted in the planning, implementation, and evaluation of programs, obtained mean ratings of 4.65 from school heads and 4.34 from teachers. This suggests that participatory M&E practices are actively observed, though teachers rate the practice slightly lower. This aligns with Bamberger et al. (2021), who emphasized that genuine stakeholder consultation enhances the credibility and relevance of evaluation processes, yet frontline staff may have varied experiences of actual participation.

Next, the second indicator, "establishing feedback mechanisms such as grievance systems and suggestion boxes," also received very high ratings (school heads = 4.66; teachers = 4.35). This indicates that structured channels for feedback are widely recognized within the school community. Torres and Preskill (2020) noted that feedback mechanisms are essential for participatory evaluation, as they allow stakeholders to express concerns and influence program decisions.

Meanwhile, the third indicator focuses on the involvement of LGUs, parents, and community members in activities under the School Governance and Operations Division (SGOD). School heads rated this practice at 4.69, while teachers provided a rating of 4.55. The strong agreement from both groups underscores the active role of community partners in school operations. This is supported by Cruz and Gámez (2022), who postulated that the presence of external stakeholders strengthens accountability structures and fosters shared ownership of program outcomes.

The fourth indicator, "keeping stakeholders informed of the progress of school programs and projects," is still in Very High Extent, which reflects strong communication and transparency mechanisms. According to UNESCO (2021), frequent dissemination of progress updates enhances trust and strengthens stakeholder engagement in the evaluation process. Lastly, indicator 5, which assesses the acknowledgment of stakeholder participation during meetings and programs, was rated 4.75 by school heads and 4.50 by teachers. Recognition and acknowledgment are essential in maintaining stakeholder motivation and continued involvement. Preskill and Boyle (2020) asserted that acknowledgment reinforces participatory culture and encourages sustained collaboration in M&E implementation.

In summary, the data affirm that the implementation of M&E with respect to stakeholders' participation is strong and well-integrated within school operations. The high ratings across indicators reflect effective communication, active community engagement, and inclusive decision-making processes, which are elements vital to a sustainable and participatory M&E system.

1.7 Impact

Table 1.7 shows the extent of M&E implementation as perceived by school heads and teachers in terms of the impact of the programs and projects. The results show consistently very high levels of agreement across all indicators, demonstrating that both stakeholder groups perceive M&E as indispensable in advancing educational outcomes and community development. The first indicator, "manifested changes in community literacy or educational attainment levels," indicates Very High Extent. This suggests that M&E activities substantially contribute to improving literacy outcomes and educational attainment.

Recent educational studies emphasize that systematic M&E mechanisms help schools assess progress and refine instructional strategies, leading to measurable gains in community literacy (Sanga et al., 2021). The indicator "employment or further education rates of graduates" also reflected a very positive perception, which implies that stakeholders strongly believe that projects and programs monitored effectively help improve learners' post-school pathways. This aligns with findings that school-based interventions, when continuously monitored, enhance students' readiness for higher education and employment (UNESCO, 2022).

Similarly, the "provision of access to marginalized groups" demonstrates that M&E systems highly help ensure inclusivity by identifying gaps and monitoring responses that benefit underserved learners. Contemporary research affirms that inclusive education thrives when data-driven monitoring identifies barriers and tracks the participation of marginalized populations (Hall & Theron, 2021). Meanwhile, the indicator "raising the community's socio-economic level" secondly reflected a very high perceived impact. The respondents believe that education projects, when monitored effectively, contribute to broader socio-economic development.

Lastly, the respondents rated "improvement in academic performance of learners" with high means of 4.59 (school heads) and 4.46 (teachers), both in the *Strongly Agree* category. This implies that M&E greatly supports academic improvement by ensuring that teaching strategies, interventions, and programs are continuously assessed and refined. Studies show that data-informed decision-making, which is a product of effective M&E, leads to higher learner achievement levels (Oktavia & Ahsan, 2023).

Overall, the composite means of 4.61 for school heads and 4.31 for teachers indicate a Very High Extent of Implementation. This suggests strong alignment between stakeholders' perceptions and current best practices, where M&E is regarded as a vital component in ensuring that educational programs produce meaningful, measurable, and sustainable impacts. These findings reflect global trends emphasizing that robust M&E

systems enhance program efficiency, relevance, and long-term outcomes (World Bank, 2023).

1.8 Monitoring and Data Quality

Table 1.8 presents the extent of implementation of M&E, focusing on monitoring processes and data quality. The results reveal consistently very high weighted means across all indicators, suggesting that both groups perceive M&E practices in schools as being implemented with strong adherence to accuracy, timeliness, and data integrity, which are key components of an effective M&E system. The first indicator, “submission of M&E reports regularly and on time,” interpreted as Strongly Agree and categorized under Very High Extent, suggests that timely reporting is a well-established practice among school personnel.

Timeliness in reporting is essential because regular monitoring enables early identification of gaps and supports evidence-based decision-making (Kusek & Rist, 2021). Secondly, “utilization of authentic and updated data in the decision-making process” also implies that current, reliable information is consistently used to guide actions and planning in the school context. The use of valid and updated data strengthens program relevance and effectiveness by ensuring alignment with actual school conditions (World Bank, 2023).

Meanwhile, the third indicator, “reporting accurate and consistent data versus actual results,” reflected strong adherence to data accuracy and consistency, which are critical for reliable monitoring. According to UNESCO (2022), maintaining accuracy in educational data enhances accountability and ensures that interventions are evaluated based on truthful and verifiable information. The fourth indicator, “checking data accuracy,” indicates that validation and verification of data are standard practices within schools’ M&E processes.

Research emphasizes that data verification is central to maintaining the credibility of M&E systems, preventing misinformation, and ensuring that outputs reflect the actual performance of programs (OECD, 2021). Finally, “safe data storage for future referrals” shows a very high extent of implementation, which signifies that schools value the security and proper documentation of data for future analysis. Data stewardship, including secure storage and retrieval, is essential to maintaining long-term institutional memory and sustaining continuous improvement efforts (Santos & Jabar, 2024).

In summary, the findings affirm that schools demonstrate strong compliance with M&E standards, especially in areas involving data quality, reporting, verification, and secure documentation. These practices contribute to a credible and effective M&E system that supports sound decision-making and sustained improvements in school performance.

2. Effectiveness and sustainability of the DepEd programs and projects as perceived by school heads and teachers

The effectiveness and sustainability of DepEd programs and projects were assessed by both school heads and teachers at a Very High Extent across all dimensions measured. The overall average mean scores of 4.47 for school heads and 4.30 for teachers both correspond to the interpretation of Very High Extent (VHE). The school heads rated stakeholder participation highest at 4.51, while “equity and inclusiveness” was rated much lower at 4.42. Teachers rated equity and inclusiveness the highest, with a mean of 4.41, while impact received the lowest rating at 4.21. Despite the differences in ratings by both respondents, the results indicate a strong consensus that the M&E systems are functioning at an optimal level across all evaluated dimensions.

The results indicated that the programs and projects are seen as highly responsive to DepEd priorities and stakeholder needs. It suggested that the initiatives are perceived as strongly contributing to intended educational results, reflecting very high perceptions of how resources, timelines, and processes are managed in carrying out these programs. The results also imply that many interventions are being integrated into regular school systems and are likely to endure beyond initial implementation, with strong agreement that the programs are designed to serve diverse and marginalized learners. The teachers highlighted active engagement of parents, LGUs, and community partners in supporting DepEd initiatives, while both groups perceive substantial positive changes in learners and the wider school community as a result of these efforts.

3. Relationship Between the Extent of Implementation of M&E and its extent of effectiveness

Table 3 presents the test on the relationship between the extent of implementation of M&E and its extent of effectiveness. The data reveal an overall Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.7225, which is interpreted as a Very Strong Relationship. All calculated r -values for the individual dimensions, ranging from 0.6115 to 0.7608, surpass the critical value of 0.2732 at a 0.05 significance level, leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) across all variables. This finding indicates that there is a statistically significant relationship between how M&E is implemented and how effective it is perceived to be.

The strongest relationship was observed in the dimension of Equity & Inclusiveness ($r = 0.7608$), followed by Monitoring & Data Quality ($r = 0.7475$), both of which fall into the "Very Strong" category. This result signifies that as M&E activities for these specific areas are more rigorously implemented, their perceived impact on school governance becomes markedly more evident. According to Mertens and Wilson (2025), the effectiveness of an evaluation system is fundamentally tied to the quality of its execution; when implementation is comprehensive, the resulting data becomes a more powerful and credible tool for institutional improvement.

Furthermore, dimensions such as Effectiveness of Outcomes ($r = 0.6897$) and Sustainability & Institutionalization ($r = 0.6758$) showed "Strong" relationships. This high

degree of correlation implies that the systematic application of M&E protocols directly facilitates the achievement of educational goals and the embedding of programs into the regular school system. As noted by Patton (2021), the "utilization-focus" of an evaluation system is maximized when there is a clear, functional link between daily evaluative actions and the perceived utility of the findings for decision-making.

In summary, the results in Table 3 affirm that the extent of M&E implementation is a critical predictor of its effectiveness. The significant r-values suggest that the more consistently and thoroughly school heads and teachers perform M&E activities, the more effective these programs become in driving strategic alignment, stakeholder engagement, and positive educational impact.

4. Difference in the Assessment of School Heads and Teachers as to the Extent of Implementation of M&E

Table 4 presents the test on the significant difference in the perceptions of school heads and teachers as to the extent of implementation of M&E. The overall results show a p-value of 0.002, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. This led to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating a statistically significant difference between the two respondent groups regarding the extent to which M&E is implemented across the division.

Statistical significance was observed across every individual dimension of implementation: Relevance & Alignment: $p = 0.001$, Effectiveness of Outcomes: $p = 0.0001$, Efficiency of Implementation: $p = 0.011$, Sustainability & Institutionalization: $p = 0.006$, Equity & Inclusiveness: $p = 0.031$, Stakeholders' Participation: $p = 0.001$, Impact of the Project & Programs: $p = 0.002$, Monitoring & Data Quality: $p = 0.005$.

In every category, the school heads assigned higher mean scores than teachers. For instance, the school heads rated "Relevance & Alignment" at 4.72 compared to the teachers' 4.42, and "Sustainability & Institutionalization" at 4.64 versus 4.37. This disparity is often attributed to the different organizational roles and vantage points of the respondents. According to Bush (2020), school leaders often hold more optimistic views of implementation because they are primarily responsible for the strategic planning and high-level reporting of these initiatives. Teachers, conversely, assess implementation through the practical lens of daily classroom execution and may be more attuned to localized challenges that hinder full program integration.

Correspondingly, Harris and Jones (2020) argued that "distributed leadership" gaps can lead to such perceptual differences; when implementation is experienced as a top-down mandate rather than a collaborative process, those on the front lines (teachers) may perceive the reality of that implementation as less robust than those at the administrative level. Despite these significant differences, it is important to note that both groups still rated the implementation within the "Very High Extent" range, indicating that while they differ on the degree, they agree on the high quality of the overall effort.

5. Difference in School Heads' and Teachers' Participation as to the Extent of Effectiveness of M&E.

Table 5 presents the test on the significant difference in the perceptions of school heads and teachers as to the extent of effectiveness of M&E. The overall data show a p-value of 0.019, which is lower than the 0.05 significance level, leading to the decision to reject the null hypothesis (H_0). This indicates that there is a significant difference between how school heads and teachers overall perceive the effectiveness of the M&E programs under the SGOD.

The specific dimensions that showed statistically significant differences include: a) Effectiveness of Outcomes - This area showed a significant difference ($p = 0.005$), with school heads reporting a mean of 4.46 compared to 4.24 from teachers; b) Stakeholders' Participation - A significant difference was noted ($p = 0.012$), where school heads (4.51) perceived engagement more highly than teachers (4.29); and c) Impact of the Project & Programs - The difference was significant ($p = 0.015$), with school heads rating impact at 4.46 and teachers at 4.21.

Conversely, several dimensions did not show a significant difference at the 0.05 level, including Relevance & Alignment ($p = 0.089$), Efficiency of Implementation ($p = 0.067$), Sustainability & Institutionalization ($p = 0.127$), Equity & Inclusiveness ($p = 0.073$), and Monitoring & Data Quality ($p = 0.066$). The consistent pattern of school heads assigning higher mean scores than teachers across all variables reflects a common administrative trend. According to Bamberger et al. (2021), administrators often have a more favorable perception of institutional systems due to their involvement in high-level planning and oversight. Teachers, however, may offer more conservative ratings based on the practical challenges and direct instructional realities they face daily. Despite these differences in perspective, both groups generally agree that the M&E systems are highly effective, as indicated by their respective composite means.

Conclusions

Based on the comprehensive findings of this study, several significant conclusions can be drawn regarding the implementation, effectiveness, and perceptions surrounding M&E practices within the DepEd Dumaguete. Firstly, M&E is not only being implemented to a considerable degree but is also perceived as contributing positively to the outcomes and sustainability of educational initiatives. The fundamental principles and processes of M&E are understood and valued within the educational community through tracking mechanisms, reporting results, and the exercise of transparency to ensure accountability in the delivery of programs and projects.

Secondly, M&E is not merely a procedural requirement but a vital component in ensuring that programs achieve their intended goals. There is better alignment with strategic objectives, with programs and projects being implemented systematically through clear indicators, set timelines, and feedback mechanisms in place. While both groups agree on the "Very High Extent," the differences in their perceptions suggest potential gaps in communication, understanding, or experiences with M&E. These differences could have

resulted from the distinct roles and responsibilities of school heads and teachers within the educational system. School heads may have a broader, more strategic view of M&E, being part of program policy implementation, while teachers may have focused on the practical, day-to-day implementation and its impact on their classrooms.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following are recommended:

Division Office:

1. Implement Role-Specific M&E Training Programs. Design and deliver targeted training programs for school heads and teachers, focusing on their specific roles and responsibilities in M&E. This ensures that each group has the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively contribute to the M&E process.
2. Establish a centralized M&E Data Repository. Create a secure, accessible online platform for storing and managing M&E data on various programs and projects implemented. This repository should be user-friendly to allow school heads and teachers to easily input, access, and analyze data related to program implementation and effectiveness.

School Heads:

1. Promote teacher involvement in M&E design. Involve teachers in the design and planning stages of M&E activities to ensure that their perspectives and experiences are considered. This fosters a sense of ownership and increases their engagement in the M&E process.
2. Allocate resources for M&E activities. Dedicate sufficient time, funding, and personnel to support M&E activities within the school. This includes providing teachers with the necessary resources to collect, analyze, and report data.

Teachers:

1. Actively participate in M&E training. Take advantage of M&E training opportunities offered by the Division Office or school administration. This guarantees that teachers have the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively contribute to M&E activities.
2. Collaborate with school heads on M&E implementation. Work closely with school heads to implement M&E activities effectively to ensure that data are collected accurately and reported on time.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a statement written by the author(s) in their own words, presented in paragraph form, affirming that informed consent was obtained; participants were free to withdraw from the study at any time; respondent anonymity was preserved; data privacy standards were upheld; participants' well-being was protected; no conflicts of interest were present during the study; plagiarism was strictly avoided; the interpretation of findings was free from bias; the results were used solely for research purposes; and any use of AI was fully disclosed by the author(s).

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